

GENERAL INFORMATION ABOUT THE PSYCHOLOGICAL HYGIENE OF MENTAL LABOR

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17920130>

Abstract. *This article analyzes the results of extensive research on the psychological analysis of mental labor. In the field of psychology, we have identified the causes of mental and spiritual labor psychohygiene, various psychological processes. The results of data analysis showed that mental labor psychohygiene largely depends on the mental state of a person. In the course of our research, the principles of psychohygiene and related areas of psychohygiene are studied. Information is provided about mental and physical diseases that occur in a person as a result of violations of mental labor psychohygiene. It is also recommended to perform mental development exercises to prevent violations of mental labor psychohygiene during a person's work.*

Keywords: *Mental work, psychological hygiene, mental states, stress, thinking, memory, psychological environment, motivation.*

AQLIY MEHNATNING PSIXOGIGIYENASI HAQIDA UMUMIY MA'LUMOTLAR

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada aqliy mehnatning psixogigiyenasini psixologik tahlil qilish bo'yicha keng qamrovli tadqiqotlarga asoslangan holda natijalar tahlil qilib o'tilgan.*

Psixologiya yo'nalishida aqliy va ruhiy mehnatning psixogigiyenasining kelib chiqish sabablari, har turli psixik jarayonlarni keltirib o'tganmiz. Ma'lumotlar tahlil natijalari shuni ko'rsatdiki, aqliy mehnatning psixogigiyenasi asosan insonning ruhiy holatiga bog'liq bo'ladi.

Tadqiqotimiz davomida psixogigiyenik tamoyillar va psixogigiyenaning mos ravishda yo'nalishlari o'rganib chiqiladi. Insonda aqliy mehnat psixogigiyenasi buzilishida kelib chiquvchi ruhiy va jismoniy kasalliklar haqida ma'lumot beriladi. Shuningdek, inson o'z faoliyati davomida aqliy mehnatning psixogigiyenasi buzilishini oldini olishda aqliy rivojlanish mashqlarini bajarashi tavsiya qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: *Aqliy mehnat, psixogigiyena, psixik holatlar, stress, tafakkur, xotira, psixologik muhit, motivatsiya.*

Introduction

Mental labor psychohygiene is a field that studies hygienic, psychological and physiological laws that ensure the effectiveness of labor activity, which are associated with factors such as human mental processes, perception, thinking, memory, attention, emotional stability, motivation. It analyzes the interaction between the human body, psyche and the working environment. Since mental labor is fundamentally different from physical labor, its hygienic foundations also require a separate scientific approach. During mental labor, the tension of the central nervous system, overload of mental processes, increased information flow, excessive sedentary work and the imbalance of the organizational environment directly affect human health. Therefore, mental labor psychohygiene performs many tasks, such as harmonizing a person's mental state with his physical health, increasing labor productivity, and protecting against professional fatigue and stress. The process of mental labor is based mainly on complex neurophysiological activity in the brain, in which stability of attention, accuracy of perception, active memory, consistency of logical thinking, speed of decision-making and emotional balance are of great importance.

Psychohygiene provides protection of a person from excessive mental stress by determining the physiological limits of these processes, optimal levels of load, and the ratio of work and rest. Because excessive mental load leads to disorders in the functioning of the nervous system, dispersion of attention, memory loss, increased emotional lability, insomnia, chronic fatigue syndrome and psychosomatic diseases. In the psychohygiene of mental labor, it is very important to properly organize activities, ensure that the workplace meets ergonomic standards, and maintain external factors such as lighting, ventilation, temperature, noise and electromagnetic fields at an optimal level. If these factors go beyond the norm, they negatively affect a person's intellectual activity, mood, stress susceptibility and productivity. People engaged in mental work often work sitting in one place for a long time, which puts an excessive load on the cardiovascular system, respiratory system and musculoskeletal system. Therefore, psychohygiene studies not only mental processes, but also the balance of physical activity and recommends the formation of a healthy lifestyle that is compatible with mental work. In particular, the widespread use of computer technology increases the information load, puts significant pressure on the organs of vision, nervous system and mental state. As a result, people experience decreased vision, headaches, muscle tension, emotional fatigue or apathy.

Psychohygiene of mental work also deeply studies factors such as how a person behaves during work, chooses a work strategy, how the motivation system works, and maintains psychological stability. The personal characteristics of a person, temperament type, stress resistance, self-control, emotional intelligence play an important role in the effectiveness of mental work.

Therefore, psychological hygiene is also aimed at strengthening the psychological resources of a person. One of the principles of organizing work in the psychological hygiene of mental work is the scientific distribution of working time and rest. With constant mental activity, the psychophysiological resources of the body begin to run out quickly, attention weakens, and the supply of oxygen to organs deteriorates, which leads to mental and physical fatigue.

Therefore, short breaks, active rest, eye exercises, muscle relaxation exercises, and respiratory hygiene are important hygienic measures. The effectiveness of mental work is also inextricably linked with a person's biological rhythms. Studies show that incomplete sleep, evening tension, and prolonged stress not only reduce the effectiveness of mental work, but also weaken the body's immune system. Psychohygiene offers sleep hygiene, rest regimen, and stress prevention methods to regulate these processes. Stress in people engaged in intellectual work is often associated with an abundance of information, lack of time, high responsibility, unclear tasks, high demands, and emotional pressure.

In such situations, psychohygiene recommends using scientifically based stress management methods, including psychological autogenic exercises, meditation, exercises that activate alpha waves of the brain, deep breathing techniques, and exercises for sequential muscle relaxation. In addition, factors such as a healthy psychological climate in the work environment, positive communication in the team, mutual respect, and support also play an important role in the effectiveness of intellectual work. Since intellectual work requires intelligence, creative thinking, strategic thinking, and logical analysis, psychohygiene also studies the creation of favorable conditions for the development of creative processes. A person's creative potential is directly related to a good mood, broad thinking, a stress-free environment, and intrinsic motivation. Therefore, psychological hygiene also includes psychological mechanisms for supporting creative activity.

Nutrition is also of great importance in mental work, because if there is a lack of substances necessary for brain activity, such as glucose, magnesium vitamins, B vitamins, thinking processes slow down, memory weakens, and attention stability is impaired. Therefore, psychological hygiene also teaches scientifically based nutrition principles. In addition, the water drinking regime is also important in mental work, because dehydration increases attention, headaches, and fatigue.

The motivation, professional satisfaction, and goal orientation of people engaged in mental work are also of particular importance for psychological hygiene. Lack of motivation reduces the effectiveness of activities, limits achievements, and accelerates psychological fatigue. Therefore, psychological hygiene studies areas such as supporting internal motivation, correctly setting goals, and encouraging the pursuit of professional growth and self-development.

The psychohygiene of intellectual labor is based on the sciences of pedagogy, psychology, medicine, physiology, ergonomics, neurobiology and sociology. By combining these sciences, the most favorable working conditions for human activity, mechanisms of psychological stability and ways to strengthen mental health are determined. Today, with the development of information technologies, the volume of intellectual labor is increasing sharply, which further increases the importance of psychohygiene issues. Since in our time most of the information comes through digital devices, new psychohygiene principles have emerged, such as digital hygiene, screen time control and protection from excessive information flow. Another important area of the psychohygiene of intellectual labor is the prevention of professional burnout. Professional burnout syndrome is characterized by emotional exhaustion, depletion of personal resources, decreased motivation and a sharp decrease in professional efficiency.

Psychohygiene offers measures such as timely identification of factors that develop this syndrome, balancing the workload, providing psychological support, and using anti-stress methods. Self-management skills of the individual are also of great importance in mental labor hygiene. Time management, prioritizing tasks, avoiding multitasking, using concentration techniques, and developing discipline increase cognitive efficiency and reduce stress. The mental health of people engaged in mental labor should be constantly monitored, since mental stability directly determines the quality of work. Psychohygiene offers the scientific basis for psychological diagnostics, psychoprophylaxis, psychological counseling, and creating a healthy psychological environment in this regard. In addition, the psychohygiene of mental labor is a broad scientific field that serves to fully realize a person's intellectual potential, maintain his mental and physical health, increase the efficiency of professional activity, and prevent fatigue.

The complexity of mental labor, the increasing information load from year to year, and the limitation of human psychic resources further increase the relevance of the issues of psychohygiene, and scientific research in this area is increasingly expanding. In this regard, psychohygiene is a strategically important scientific direction that supports not only individual healthy activity, but also the intellectual potential of society. Since the effectiveness of the mental labor process is intricately related to the psychophysiological characteristics of a person, individual cognitive capabilities, and external socio-cultural factors, psychohygiene deeply studies the balance between these factors. The type of higher nervous activity of a person, the type of temperament, the individual's stress resistance, emotional stability, and the level of internal motivation determine the adaptation to mental labor. Psychohygiene develops scientific recommendations aimed at optimizing mental work, taking into account these individual differences.

The workplace of a person engaged in mental work must fully meet ergonomic requirements, since an improperly organized working environment not only causes physical discomfort, but also leads to mental stress, chronic fatigue, distraction and reduced productivity.

The height of the desk, the shape and rigidity of the chair, the distance from the monitor, the location of the keyboard, the level of lighting are factors of great importance in the process of mental work. Memory processes also play an important role in mental work. The greater the flow of information coming to a person, the greater the load on the memory systems. Overexertion of memory processes can lead to a decrease in mental efficiency, increased forgetfulness and a slowdown in the process of assimilation of new information. Psychological hygiene scientifically studies factors such as healthy sleep, rest, proper nutrition, consumption of substances that increase the metabolic activity of the brain, and stress reduction to support memory processes. In addition to reproductive memory, exercises that activate logical and associative memory processes also play an important role in memory hygiene.

These exercises increase neuroplasticity, that is, the flexibility of brain neurons, form new neural connections, and contribute to more effective mental activity. Another important aspect of mental work is the level of motivation and internal mental energy. The more specific and specific a person's goals are, the more effective they are in the process of mental work.

Psychological hygiene emphasizes the need to correctly set goals in the formation of motivation, develop mechanisms for internal satisfaction for them, form a reward system, and create favorable conditions for professional growth. When motivation is lacking, apathy, lethargy, and distraction are observed in the process of mental work, which reduces labor productivity. Therefore, psychological hygiene studies the mechanisms of supporting the internal resources of the individual and replenishing psychological energy.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be said that, based on the analytical results of psychological research on the psychohygiene of mental labor, it is advisable to organize mental and psychological exercises based on the mental state of a person. Modern psychological research has shown that people who constantly work with a high level of mental activity are at a very high risk of mental stress and stress. Also, over time, such conditions cause various mental illnesses. By combining mental labor with physical labor, it is possible to reduce the listed illnesses. In the correct formation of the psychohygiene of mental labor, it is advisable to form the thinking and worldview of the individual.

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